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Dioxouranium(II) and Thorium(IV) Complexes with Multidentate Schiff Bases derived from 1,8-Diaminonaphthalene

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HERE we report the dioxouranium(II) and thorium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases obtained by the condensation of 1,8-diaminonaphthalene with benzaldehyde (1), salicylaldehyde (2) and vanillin (3).

- 1; R=R'=H (DAN-Benz)
2; R=OH, R'=H (DAN-Sal)
3; R=OH, R'=OCH₃ (DAN-Van)

Experimental

Hydrated thorium(IV) nitrate, uranyl nitrate hexahydrate (B.D.H.) and 1,8-diaminonaphthalene (Fluka) were used. Benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and vanillin were used after purification. The ligands were prepared according to the literature methods¹.

Synthesis of complexes: Equimolar quantities of uranyl or thorium nitrate in ethanol were refluxed with the ligand in ethanol for ~1 h. The coloured complexes separated on cooling. The complexes formed were suction-filtered, washed thoroughly with ethanol, then with ether and finally dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride.

Uranium and thorium contents in complexes were determined gravimetrically² as U₂O₅ and ThO₂. Nitrogen was estimated microanalytically by Dumas' method.

Physicochemical measurements: Conductance measurements were done with Elco CM-82 conductivity bridge using DMF as solvent. Infrared spectra (KBr) of the complexes and ligands were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 81 spectrometer in the region 4000–180 cm⁻¹. The results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The limited solubility of complexes in common organic solvents did not permit the determination of their molecular weights, low molar conductance values indicate the complexes to be non-electrolytes³.

An examination of the IR spectra of the free ligand and those of complexes indicated similarity although in many cases the ligand bands were shifted due to lattice effects or due to departure from idealised symmetry^{4,5}. The IR spectra of ligands 2 and 3 show a broad weak band at ~2900 cm⁻¹ instead of a strong band at ~3100 cm⁻¹ due to the phenolic OH group. This may be due to the intra-molecular hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl hydrogen and nitrogen of the azomethine group forming the stable six membered ring⁶. The complexes of Sl. nos. 2, 3, 5 and 6 (Table 1) also do not show the OH group frequency thereby indicating that the OH group of the Schiff base 2 and 3 is utilised in the formation of M—O bond. This is further supported by the shift of C—O frequency from ~1290 cm⁻¹ to ~1380 cm⁻¹ in these complexes^{6,7}. A strong band found in the region 1620–1590 cm⁻¹ is assignable to the C=N stretch of Schiff bases. The shifting of the ν_{C=N} to high frequency region (1640–1630 cm⁻¹) in complexes suggests the coordination to the central metal atom through the nitrogen of the azomethine group^{6,7}. As expected^{8,9} the ν₃ and ν₁ vibrational modes of uranyl ions in complexes of Sl. nos. 1–3 (Table 1) appeared at 935–925 and 835–820 cm⁻¹,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)		Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		Metal	N	
1.	[UO ₂ (DAN-Benz)(NO ₃) ₂]	32.41 (32.69)	7.61 (7.69)	35
2.	[UO ₂ (DAN-Sal)]	34.33 (37.53)	6.10 (4.41)	52
3.	[UO ₂ (DAN-Van)]	32.89 (34.29)	5.83 (4.03)	51
4.	[Th(DAN-Benz)(NO ₃) ₄]	28.25 (28.50)	9.97 (10.31)	55
5.	[Th(DAN-Sal)(NO ₃) ₃]	29.61 (32.22)	9.17 (7.77)	53
6.	[Th(DAN-Van)(NO ₃) ₃]	27.93 (29.74)	8.18 (7.17)	51

respectively. The free nitrate bands appearing at 1035–970 cm^{-1} was split into two bands, 1530–1480 and 1290–1250 cm^{-1} on coordination¹⁰. It was difficult to assign the 1530–1480 cm^{-1} band in the complexes as this was the region of C=C frequency also. The band appearing in the region 1260–1240 cm^{-1} in complexes of Sl. nos. 1, 4, 5 and 6 was assigned to coordinated nitrate group. The band found in the region 510–530 cm^{-1} in complexes of Sl. nos. 1–3 is ascribed to $\nu_{\text{U-N}}$ and the band at 545–450 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{Th-N}}$ in complexes of Sl. nos. 4–6 (Table 1)¹¹. The 440–460 cm^{-1} band in the complexes of Sl. nos. 2, 3, 5 and 6 was assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ modes¹².

The electronic spectra of as the complexes in solution showed no distinct bands in the region 330–750 nm. The typical electronic spectral band expected due to the UO₂^{II} group at 390–450 nm in the complexes were masked by the strong charge transfer and ligand absorption bands appearing in this region.

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Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of some Trivalent Lanthanides with Salicylidene Anthranilic Acid†

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SOME of the thermodynamic properties of lanthanides have revealed that they may be placed into two groups with Gd^{III} as the dividing species¹. In the present communication, an attempt is made to establish the relationship between some rare earth metal ions belonging to the first half of the lanthanide series, i.e. Pr^{III}(f²), Nd^{III}(f³), Sm^{III}(f⁵) and Gd^{III}(f⁷). With this view we have undertaken the potentiometric studies of complex formation of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} with salicylidene anthranilic acid (SAAA) in 50% (v/v) ethanol–water medium at two temperatures 32 and 42 ± 1° and at an approximately constant ionic strength (μ) of 0.1 M (NaClO₄).

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were either of A.R. grade or purified before use. The ligand was prepared by following the procedure as described earlier². The metal perchlorates were dissolved in 0.1 M perchloric acid solution and standardised by EDTA method³.

pH-metric titration method of Bjerrum–Calvin^{4,5} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶ was followed to determine the formation constant values. The experimental procedure is the same as mentioned

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